

A METHOD FOR THE PRODUCTION OF HIGH QUALITY ALIGNED SHORT FIBRE MATS AND THEIR COMPOSITES

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A commercially viable plant, known as the Centrifuge Process, is described which produces unidirectionally aligned discontinuous resin impregnated mats 2 metres by 1 metre to specification. The process has been exploited to produce mats of aligned short carbon fibre, glass fibre and finely divided and intimately mixed combinations of carbon high strength and high modulus fibres, and glass with high modulus carbon fibre.

With the high degree of alignment achieved with this method, composites having 50-55 per cent volume loadings can be fabricated by low pressure autoclave moulding techniques. By using high pressure match metal die moulding techniques laminates of 60 per cent fibre loading can be obtained.

The mechanical properties of carbon fibre composites fabricated from resin impregnated mats produced via this process were similar to those measured for equivalent composites made from continuous fibre. Tensile moduli of discontinuous fibre composites were within 95 per cent of the respective continuous fibre composite and the strengths within 90 per cent.

These large mats have been used successfully to fabricate gearbox shells and coupling flanges for drive shafts and are being utilised for similar applications in the air frame and aero-engine industries singularly and in conjunction with cloth material in composite structures with complex curvatures.

INTRODUCTION

In the past decade MOD, PERME, has developed methods for processing discontinuous fibres to yield reinforced composite materials which are useful for engineering construction. Commercially viable processes [1,2] have been designed and operated to sort fibres into lengths and diameter fractions and to align short fibres into parallel array.

The PERME Filtration Process [3] for the alignment of discontinuous fibres has been used successfully for a variety of materials such as chopped carbon and glass fibre, graded amosite and anthophyllite asbestos and silicon carbide whiskers. The flexural strengths and moduli of epoxy thermoset composites made from the aligned mats have been recorded. [4] The reasons and advantages of chopping continuous fibre and forming unidirectional aligned short fibre mats have been given by Dingle [5] and by Kacir.[6] They pointed out that when complicated shapes and double curvatures are to be fabricated by match die high pressure moulding techniques aligned short fibre mats have an advantage over their equivalent continuous mats. With continuous filament impregnated mats there is a danger of longitudinal displacement or transverse splitting of the sheets in the layers of prepreg during lay up or as pressure is applied unless great care is taken. Fig 1 is a simple illustration of the problem. The photograph shows a moulding of an "egg box" type structure. The shape in Fig 1a was manufactured from aligned short carbon fibre resin impregnated mat (prepreg) while that in 1b from continuous fibre material. Both prepregs were of the same weight per unit area. The shaped prepregs were oven cured but not consolidated.

Fabrics are also used for complex shapes but only where their change of orientation during shaping is either unimportant or positively favourable. Potter [7] has shown that with care unidirectional aligned short carbon fibre resin impregnated mats (prepregs) made via the Filtration Process can be stretched transversely, axially and in shear without significantly changing the fibre orientation. The short fibre prepreg material has the advantage with respect to a woven cloth that it can be formed to the profile of a mould without destroying the uniformity of the fibre distribution or orientation. Hence it is feasible to mould complicated three dimensional shapes with complex curvatures without introducing defects, misorientation or resin rich areas.

However when large structures are to be moulded from prepregs produced via the Filtration Process and using low pressure autoclave techniques it is difficult to obtain composites with high fibre volume loading. It was realised that to obtain these high loadings a higher degree of fibre alignment had to be achieved in the fibrous mat.

FILTRATION ALIGNMENT PROCESS

In the Filtration Alignment Process fibre alignment is achieved by submitting a dilute suspension of fibre in glycerol to a simple accelerating shear field. The fibre mat is formed by extruding the suspension of fibre through a slit in a V-shaped trough which is reciprocated over a filter bed. The carrier liquid is removed rapidly by strong suction to prevent the deposited fibres flowing out of their aligned relationship. A set rest period is allowed between each deposition step for filtration. The weight of fibre deposited depends upon the number of reciprocations. Difficulties arise when the process is employed to build up thick, well aligned fibre mats in a reasonable time. During lay down as the thickness of the mat increases the resistance to filtration increases which consequently results in the carrier liquid not being removed sufficiently quickly to prevent serious misalignment of the fibres. If the carrier liquid is not removed rapidly from the deposition layer a possibility exists for random liquid movement leading to fibre misorientation as the fibres follow the liquid path. This can only be overcome by gradually increasing the rest periods between each reciprocation of the depositing head. Unfortunately this action decreases the rate of production to an economically unacceptable rate.

Fig 1a "Egg-Box" structure
moulded from aligned
discontinuous carbon
fibre prepreg

Fig 1b "Egg-box" structure
moulded from
continuous fibre prepreg

The degree of fibre alignment in the extruded sheet can be improved by using very dilute fibre suspensions as reported by Dingle. [5] But this again reduces the production rate to an uneconomical level.

Another method to improve the fibre alignment in the extruded sheet is to divide the alignment slit into small sections. This again is an unacceptable solution to the problem because this innovation leads to a decrease in the weight per unit area of fibre in the mat immediately beneath the dividing partitions. This introduces inherent defects into the mat.

CENTRIFUGE ALIGNMENT PROCESS

In recent years a new process known as the Centrifuge Alignment Process [8] has been developed at PERME which overcomes these problems. The concepts are basically the same as used in the original Filtration Plant. Alignment is achieved by submitting a suspension of fibres in glycerine to a velocity gradient. Instead of extruding through a slit the slurry is ejected from a tapered nozzle. The fibres in the resulting free unbounded slurry jet are aligned in the direction of flow. Pittman and Harris [9] have shown that by using a nozzle rather than a slit superior fibre alignment can be achieved.

The mat is formed by reciprocating the resulting jet over a permeable cylindrical surface, moving with an angular velocity sufficient to pass the carrier medium rapidly through the surface by centrifugal force. This leaves a layer of highly aligned fibres on the permeable surface. By increasing the angular velocity as the thickness of the aligned fibre mats increase the rate of removal of the dispersion medium can be maintained at the optimum value preventing misalignment of newly deposited aligned fibres.

Small Prototype Centrifuge Alignment Plant

Fig 2 shows a photograph of the prototype Centrifuge Alignment Plant. The equipment consists of three main sections (a) a pressurised feed tank, (b) a centrifuge bowl rotating about a horizontal axis and (c) an alignment head. The basic apparatus is a modified peeler centrifuge. The diameter of the bowl is approximately 42 cm and the depth 17 cm. The permeable surface is made from perforated stainless steel plate. To aid the harvesting of the mat a 100 mesh nylon gauze is pinned on top of the perforated plate so that at the end of a run the nylon gauze can be removed with the mat without disturbing the fibre alignment. To maintain a homogeneous suspension in the feed tank the suspension is gently stirred with a reciprocating air driven paddle. To avoid flocculation and ensure good fibre dispersion during flow to the alignment nozzle an in-line rotating cone-mixer was inserted between the feed tank and the alignment head.

Mats 120 cm long and 12 cm wide are produced on this plant. Fig 3 shows a photograph of a section of an aligned short carbon fibre mat produced by this process and demonstrates the high degree of alignment that can be achieved with this method.

VOLUME PACKING OF ALIGNED FIBRES

The standard test developed as a product control for assessing the degree of alignment achieved in the mats is to compare the relationship between the change of percentage volume packing with the applied consolidation pressure. Fig 4 is an illustration of this type of relationship. It was measured for a mat produced from 3 mm long Courtauld HTS fibre. For the consolidation pressure of 0.6894 MN m^{-2} , which is the normal working pressure for most industrial autoclaves, the volume packing is 50 per cent after which the packing gradually increases to an asymptotic value of 60 per cent at a pressure of 6.894 MN m^{-2} which is a pressure normally used in high pressure mouldings.

Fig 2 Small Centrifuge Alignment Plant

Fig 3 Aligned Short Carbon Fibre Mat Produced on Centrifuge Plant

For comparison purposes a pressure-packing graph for standard mats produced via the Filtration Plant is also included in Fig 4. At equal pressures the respective fibre volumes are considerably lower than that measured for the standard Centrifuge material. Even under optimised conditions the mats produced on the Filtration Plant as shown in Fig 4 still do not pack as well as those produced via the Centrifuge Process. These graphs illustrate the improvement in fibre alignment that can be gained by using a nozzle rather than a slit for alignment purposes.

Parratt [10] has analysed the packing of aligned fibrous mats. Starting with the theoretical maximum of 91 percent for close packed parallel cylinders he estimated that a value of 70 percent would be more realistic packing limit for the practical case involving unidirectional aligned continuous fibre mats. This is because real fibres are seldom perfectly close packed. Included in Fig 4 is the relationship for the pressure-volume packing for a continuous fibre mat. At the low pressure end of the plot which can be considered as the region representing the natural packing of the fibres, the value is near to Parratt's suggested figure. At the higher pressures the curve does reach an asymptotic value of 70 percent confirming Parratt's estimations. Aligned discontinuous fibres have inherently lower packing fractions unless the fibre ends are perfectly butted end to end. In practice gaps between fibre ends and fibre overlapping will always occur. Parratt assuming the most probable gap between fibre ends estimated volume packing for mats of aligned short fibres to be 0.67 of 70 percent. This is of the same order of magnitude measured at low pressures for the aligned short carbon fibre mats.

From these arguments it is assumed that the fibre alignment in mats produced by the Centrifuge Plant is as good as that achieved by systems used for producing continuous fibre mats and must be close to the practical maximum.

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF ALIGNED SHORT FIBRE COMPOSITES

Having developed a plant such as the Centrifuge Process, which is basically a batch process, concern is always expressed regarding the process control, and hence the variability of the mechanical properties of the resulting composites. Another question which is also asked is how do the mechanical properties of aligned short fibre composites compare with those of their respective continuous laminates.

To alleviate this concern and to settle the question of comparisons a programme was devised to cover both these items.

Numerous resin impregnated mats were prepared from 3 mm long Courtaulds HTS carbon fibre and Shell DX210 BF₄₀₀ resin system and stored in a refrigerator. Simultaneously at an independent laboratory unidirectionally aligned continuous fibre prepreg material was prepared using fibre and resin from the same batches.

Composites were fabricated from these prepregs using match metal die hot compression moulding techniques using enclosed moulds and stops to control the composite thickness. The aligned short fibre prepregs were cut into preforms of dimensions 17.5 cm and 11.4 cm. These were then thoroughly mixed. The preforms were loaded into a cold tool and placed between the cold platens of a hydraulic press. The pressing procedure has been described elsewhere. [4]

Eighteen composites were moulded of thickness 2 ± 0.5 mm. Nine composites had a nominal fibre volume loading of 50 ± 2 percent and nine of 55 ± 2 percent. The internal quality of each composite was examined through the thickness direction by ultrasonic techniques using a focussed probe. The variation in attenuation of a 10 MHz compression wave was observed along the axial direction of the specimen. The whole width of the specimen was scanned at 0.5 mm intervals. The attenuation for the boards ranged from 6 to 26 dB. Within the limits of the apparatus no faults or delaminations were detected in any of the laminates.

Eighteen composites of the same dimensions and nominal fibre volume loadings were fabricated from continuous fibre prepreg by Rotoway Components Ltd.

Fig 4 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VOLUME PACKING AND CONSOLIDATION PRESSURE FOR ALIGNED COURTAIDS HTS CARBON FIBRE MATS

Fig 5 DISTRIBUTION OF TENSILE STRENGTHS OF CONTINUOUS AND DISCONTINUOUS ALIGNED CARBON FIBRE EPOXY COMPOSITES

The fibre volume loadings and percentage voids for each board were determined by the standard acid digestion techniques as specified in MOD Specification NM 547.

The tensile properties of all the laminates were measured by an independent authority AQD Harefield. The tests were carried out as specified in MOD(PE) Specification NM 565.

Eight tensile specimens were prepared from each panel. Figs 5 and 6 show histograms of all the results measured for the panels of nominal 50 per cent volume loading after they had been normalised to 50 per cent using the simple law of mixtures rule. Table 1 gives the grand means, standard deviations and coefficient of variation for these normalised values. The values are the means of 72 tensile specimens cut from 9 separate panels.

The grand mean value for the tensile strength of the discontinuous fibre composite is 91 per cent of the respective continuous. The modulus is 95 per cent.

The coefficients of variation for the grand mean strengths and moduli for the discontinuous fibre laminates were of the same order of magnitude as their respective continuous composites.

The comparison of continuous to discontinuous at 55 per cent volume shows a larger difference to that found for the 50 per cent volume comparison. No definite reason can be found to account for this loss. It was thought that it might be due to a lower fibre aspect ratio in the higher volume loaded composite thereby decreasing the efficiency of the load transfer mechanism. Fibres were extracted from laminates of both volume loadings and within experimental error the length distribution of the fibres from either loading were the same.

The tensile strengths measured in this investigation for the discontinuous composites were well above those predicted by the theory of Lovelace and Tsai. [7] The values are more consistent with Lockett's modified shear lag theory. [72]

For a unidirectional aligned discontinuous fibre composite having a random distribution of fibre ends Lockett's idealised analysis predicted strengths in excess of 87 per cent of those of a composite with continuous reinforcement. He suggested that it should be possible to obtain strengths in excess of 90 per cent of those achieved with continuous fibre reinforcement. In the light of Lockett's hypothesis it is assumed that values quoted in this report for aligned discontinuous fibre composites must be very close to the maximum practical values.

CENTRIFUGE PROCESS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF LARGE SHEETS OF ALIGNED SHORT FIBRE RESIN IMPREGNATED MATS

Alignment Plant

On the strength of these good mechanical properties it was decided to construct a plant to produce much larger sheets of aligned short fibre mat using the same basic concepts of the plant shown in Fig 2.

Fig 7 shows the plant that was constructed and is at present in operation producing aligned fibre mats of dimensions 2 x 1 metres of laminate moulding thicknesses varying from 0.0762 mm to 0.508 mm. The diameter of the perforated drum is 66 cm and is open at both ends. The drum is driven on external rollers about a horizontal axis. A multiple number of alignment nozzles are used and during fibre lay down all the nozzles are allowed to travel completely through the drum on each reciprocation of the alignment head. Under working conditions the nozzles are only depositing for part of their travelling time in contrast to the original prototype model in which the nozzle was depositing for 100 per cent of its travelling time. This action ensures uniform fibre weight distribution in the mat.

The feed supply to the nozzles is basically the same as that used in the small

TABLE 1

Comparison of Tensile Properties of Unidirectionally Aligned Discontinuous and
Continuous Carbon Fibre Epoxy Resin Composites

Nominal Fibre Volume Loading %	Type of Fibre	Tensile Modulus			Ultimate Tensile Strength		
		Mean GN m ⁻²	Standard Deviation GN m ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation %	Mean MN m ⁻²	Standard Deviation MN m ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation %
50	Discontinuous	110	4.3	3.9	1148	61.2	5.3
50	Continuous	116	2.9	2.5	1260	40.9	3.2
55	Discontinuous	119	3.2	2.7	1211	31.5	2.6
55	Continuous	128	5.2	4.1	1425	71.4	5.0

Fig 6 DISTRIBUTION OF TENSILE MODULI OF CONTINUOUS AND DISCONTINUOUS ALIGNED CARBON FIBRE EPOXY COMPOSITES

Fig 7 Large Centrifuge Alignment Plant

plant. The fibre and glycerine are gently mixed together in a large container and pumped into the pressure feed tanks. These supply the nozzles with the fibre slurry via an in-line fibre disperser as before. To maintain a continuous supply of slurry to the nozzle two feed tanks are used alternately.

The procedure for operating the large centrifuge plant is the same as that used for the small plant. When the required weight of fibre has been laid down the mat is extracted from the drums and the excess glycerine is washed out with a gentle spray of water while the mat is held firmly flat on a large filter bed. The mat is then dried in an oven in preparation for resin impregnation. The packing fraction curves for carbon fibre mats produced on this plant were all similar to those measured for mats produced via the small plant. The volume per cent packing varied between 49-51 for a consolidation pressure of 0.6894 MN m^{-2} .

To check the variation in the fibre weight per unit area a 2 square metre mat was cut into $15 \times 15 \text{ cm}$ ($\pm 0.24 \text{ cm}$) squares giving a matrix of 6×12 . The coefficient of variation of the areal density of these 72 specimens was ± 5.4 per cent.

RESIN IMPREGNATION OF ALIGNED MATS

The dry fibre mats are impregnated with resin from solvent solution or by resin film techniques.

Wet Impregnation

The 2×1 metre mat is placed on a flat horizontal table. This is moved forward slowly beneath a resin depositing head. This consists of a number of jets which are reciprocated over the mat transversely to the direction of motion of the mat. The viscosity and flow rate of the resin solution, the speeds of the table and depositing head are set to give a complete and uniform coverage of the mat by the resin. After the impregnation step most of the solvent is allowed to evaporate at room temperature and then the mat is placed in an oven and the resin B-staged in a stream of warm air.

The percentage weight of resin pick-up is fairly constant for any particular mat thickness therefore the ratio of weight of resin to fibre in the prepreg material can easily be varied by altering the weight of resin in the solvent solution. The percentage weight ratio of resin to fibre for the standard mats is 50:50 but as mentioned other ratios can easily be obtained.

To check the variation of the resin weight in a mat about a mean the 2×1 metre mat was again chopped into squares $15 \times 15 \text{ cm}$ and weighed. All the resin from each square was extracted by acid digestion and the mat re-weighed. The difference gave the percentage of resin. For the 72 specimens the coefficient of variation about a mean percentage weight/unit area was ± 1.5 per cent.

Film Impregnation

The procedure for resin film impregnation is slightly different. The dry mat is impregnated with 2 per cent by weight of resin as previously described. A sandwich is made of the mat with a sheet of resin film each side. This is heated between the hot platters of a press and the hot resin is squeezed into the fibrous mat. If the binder system is not used the short fibres on pressing will move from their original preferred orientation.

A typical aligned short fibre prepreg is shown in Fig 8. The dimensions of the sheet are approximately $2 \times 1 \text{ m} \times 0.125 \text{ mm}$ thick. The fibres are 3 mm long Courtaulds HTS carbon fibre and the matrix is Ciba-Geigy 914 film resin system.

Large sheets of prepreg are being manufactured from discontinuous high strength and high modulus carbon fibre, glass and homogeneous binary and tertiary mixes of these fibres.

Fig 8 Prepreg produced via
Centrifuge Alignment
Process

Fig 9 Micrograph cross-section of a glass/carbon
HMS hybrid composite

Table 2 gives the mechanical properties of 2 mm thick composites made from these fibres and Giba-Geigy 914 film epoxy resin system using autoclave techniques. The autoclave pressure was 0.6844 MN m^{-2} . Bleed layers were used for all laminations. The fibre volume loading were all 50 ± 2 per cent as would be expected from the data presented in Fig 4 for the packing of these materials. The values in Table 2 have been normalised to 50 per cent loading. These values are similar in magnitude as those measured for composites fabricated by compression moulding techniques.

EXPLOITATION OF THE CENTRIFUGE PROCESS FOR THE PREPARATION OF MIXED FIBRE STRUCTURES

Chamis and Lark [13] have reviewed the advantages of hybrid composite structures made from continuous fibre over the more conventional continuous fibre laminates. By using hybrids they have argued that it is possible to obtain a viable compromise between mechanical properties and cost to meet specified design requirements.

Phillips [14] has described the virtues of hybrids formed by the inter-weaving of high strength carbon fibre and glass fibre. His results help in the acceptance of the load sharing principle for analysis of the strengths of these materials. Unfortunately at the present time this method for the manufacture of hybrid mats of mixed fibres cannot be used with brittle fibres.

In the case of the Centrifuge Alignment Plant the fabricator is presented with a unique method for easily producing sheet material of finely divided and intimately mixed combinations of two or more different fibres. The method does not have the problems associated with the weaving of brittle fibres.

Parratt et al [15] have demonstrated that with this type of hybrid mixture produced by the Centrifuge Plant brittle fibres can be made to carry loads beyond their usual strength as a reinforcement, ie the linear part of the hybrid stress-strain curve is more extensive than expected. Results measured on finely mixed hybrids of Courtaulds HMS/HTS 3 mm long carbon fibres have shown that the lower strain to break fibre exhibits different levels of strength, depending on their surroundings. They showed that when the brittle Courtaulds HMS fibre is well protected they approach the average strength of HMS fibre (about 1.1% strain).

Combinations of HMS and glass have also been investigated. In some respects the results from these investigations confirm those measured by Richter. [16] For certain combinations a large increase in the fracture toughness of the brittle fibre can be realised. Fig 9 is a micrograph of a cross-section of a mixed glass/carbon HMS composite. It illustrates the good fibre mixing that can be obtained in hybrid structures produced via this method. Also with these structures a bonus is obtained by using the cheaper glass fibre in place of the high cost carbon fibre. It reduces the material costs substantially making these materials attractive on a cost performance basis.

In the carbon fibre prepreg industry large savings in material costs can also be achieved by diluting the expensive high quality carbon fibre with fibre produced by inexpensive routes. The Centrifuge Alignment Process is being operated successfully to produce mats from mixtures of these fibres. Good quality fibres are mixed with pitch carbon fibre and fibre produced in "jumbo" size tows of 160,000 filaments, without paying too high a penalty on the original properties. The process is also being used to up-grade carbon fibre recovered from waste continuous fibre prepreg which at present can be as high as 30 per cent in some industries. The results of these investigations will be reported at a later date.

TABLE 2

Mechanical Properties of Unidirectionally Aligned Discontinuous CompositesFabricated Using Autoclave Moulding Techniques

Resin System Ciba-Geigy 914 Film

Fibre Loading Nominal 50 %

	Flexural Modulus			Ultimate Flexural Strength			Interlaminar Shear Strength		
	Mean GN m ⁻²	Standard Deviation GN m ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation \pm %	Mean MN m ⁻²	Standard Deviation MN m ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation \pm %	Mean MN m ⁻²	Standard Deviation MN m ⁻²	Coefficient of Variation %
3 mm Courtaulds HMS	140	7.7	5.5	888	9.8	1.1	71	4.9	7
3 mm Courtaulds HTS	105	1.8	1.7	1226	67.4	5.5	90	7.4	8.2
3 mm Vetrotex R-Glass	32	1.5	4.6	1284	30.8	2.4	94	2.3	2.4

CONCLUSION

The Centrifuge Alignment Process can produce unidirectionally aligned discontinuous fibre mats with a degree of fibre alignment better than that achieved by the original Filtration Process without sacrificing any of the excellent drape characteristics of the original material. This better alignment was most probably obtained by using a nozzle instead of a slit. The evidence produced in this investigation suggests that the degree of fibre alignment obtained is very near the practical limit.

In the Filtration Process and processes based on the same principle, improved fibre alignment can also be achieved by extruding through a nozzle instead of a slit but the mat production rate would be greatly reduced. In the Centrifuge Process the rate is made commercially viable by using faster fluid velocities and a multiple nozzle system. This again is possible because of the more efficient fluid removal from the permeable surface.

Further development work is in progress to increase the output by improving further the efficiency of the draining surface and increasing the number of depositing nozzles.

It is also hoped to improve the unit cost for prepreg manufacture by decreasing the number of steps involved in the production of these materials by eliminating the water washing and resin impregnation stages. A reasonable amount of success has been achieved by replacing the glycerol carrier medium with a solvent resin solution giving a finished prepreg in situ. The results from these investigations will be reported at another time.

Large quantities of prepreps have been made to tight specifications from a number of different fibres and a variety of resin systems. These are being used in assessment studies on the utilisation of discontinuous fibre prepreps for fabricating helicopter gearboxes, flanges for drive shafts, rocket nozzles, rocket tube liners, and similar applications with air-frame and aero-engine industries.

Fig 10 shows a photograph of composite structure the shape of which was selected to demonstrate the fabrication characteristics of this material. The structure included most of the features such as flanges and double curvatures which are likely to be encountered in gearbox shells. The flange was moulded using a petal shape configuration lay-up and the whole structure was formed using autoclave moulding techniques.

The material can also be used as a complimentary material to clothes. The structure shown in Fig 11 is a good example of this role. This is a photograph of a coupling flange moulded from carbon fibre cloth. Layers of unidirectional aligned short carbon fibre have been interleaved with the cloth to reinforce the radial direction to accommodate any off axis loading.

REFERENCES

- 1 Parratt N J, Gooding R W, *New Technology* 1971, 46, 5.
- 2 Bagg G E G, Evans M E N, Pryde A W H, *Composites* 1969, 1, 2, 97.
- 3 UK Patent 1,249,291
- 4 Bagg G E G, Dingle L E, Edwards H, Evans M E N, Ziebland H, *British Plastics Federation Seventh International Reinforced Plastics Conference, Brighton 1970, Paper 6.*
- 5 L E Dingle, *International Conference on Carbon Fibres, London, February 1974, Paper 11.*
- 6 Kacir L, Narkis M, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, July 1975, 15, No 7, 525.
- 7 Potter K D, *Composites*, July 1979, 161.
- 8 UK Patent 1,389,539.
- 9 Harris J, Pittman J F T, *Trans Inst Chem Eng*, Oct 1973.
- 10 Parratt N J, *Fibre Reinforced Materials Technology, Van Nostrand Reinhold Co 1972.*

- 11 Lovelace A M, Tsai S W, *Astronautics and Aeronautics*, July 1970, 56.
- 12 Lockett F J, *Conference Proc National Physical Laboratory*, Nov 1971, Paper 6.
- 13 Chamis C C, Lark R F, *Eighteenth Annual Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, San Diego, California, March 1977.
- 14 Phillips L N, *ICCM/2* 1978.
- 15 Edwards H, Parratt, N J, Potter K D, *ICCM/2* 1978.
- 16 Richter H, *Kunststoffe* 67 (1977) 12, 739.

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Fig 10 Demonstrator gearbox shell

Fig 11 Coupling Flange
1635